

Synthesis of silica hollow nanosphere using poly vinyl alcohol

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Abstract : Silica hollow microsphere was synthesized in presence of poly vinyl alcohol. Effect of a UV absorber, say 2,2',4,4'-tetrahydroxy benzophenone on particle growth was studied. Increase in amount of the UV absorber results in fibrous material. Same way effect of other polymers such as polyvinyl pyrrolidine and polyethylene glycol were also studied. They also give fibrous material.

Keywords : Silica hollow microsphere, polyvinyl alcohol, tetrahydroxy.

There is a great interest concerning the synthesis of hollow materials with specific structure and different compositions¹. It is due to their applications in catalysis, controlled release for drugs, dyes and perfumes, development of artificial cells and protection of biologically active agents such as proteins and enzymes². These uses are due to its properties of lower densities, high surface area and more unique optical and chemical properties. Several techniques reported for the synthesis of this materials such as nozzle reactor approaches, emulsion/phase extraction techniques and self assembly processes including layer by layer (LBL) method³.

In this paper, we present a simple pathway to fabricate silica hollow sphere. We used methyl trimethoxysilane, tetraethylorthosilicate, ammonia and water homogenized at 1000 rpm and further polyvinylalcohol was added and stirred for another 2 h gave hollow silica microsphere. UV absorber is an organic. It is used to prevent UV light from sun to skin. However it is having side effect as it touches the human body. To avoid it silica hollow sphere is employed. Normally, encapsulate UV-absorber inside the silica hollow sphere by two different ways. First one is presynthesis modification. Another is post synthesis modification. In this experiment we employed presynthesis modification. We obtain fibers instead of spheres. Influence of a UV-absorber and other polymers such as polyvinyl pyrrolidine and polyethylene glycol were studied.

Results and discussion

Synthesis of silica hollow microsphere was found from reaction with tetraethylortho silicate, methyl trimethoxy silane, ammonia, water and poly vinyl alcohol. As ammonia is immiscible with water it is mixed by homogenizer at 1000 rpm. Polyvinyl alcohol was used as a dispersant. Methyltrimethoxy silane was used as silica precipitation initiator along with ammonia.

Scanning electron microscopy images of the samples synthesized from polyvinyl alcohol shows spherical shape (Fig. 1a, 500 nm–3 μm), sample from polyvinyl pyrrolidine are fibers (Fig. 1c, 200 nm–10 μm) and sample from polyethylene glycol are also fibers (Fig. 1d, 200 nm–10 μm). The smooth internal structure of sample synthesized from polyvinyl alcohol can be seen from the picture. The white layer with dark inner diameter in SEM (Fig. 1a) reveals it is a hollow nature. Further the samples transition electron microscopic picture shows the hollow nanosphere diameter is 500 nm with the shell thickness is 50 nm (Fig. 1b). Use of UV absorber (2,2',4,4'-tetrahydroxy benzophenone) when we use poly vinyl alcohol change the morphology into fibers. Yields of the samples synthesized with different UV absorber content shows a parabolic nature. The yields are decreased by change of polymer from poly vinyl alcohol (88%) to PVP (45%) and PEG (64%).

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Fig. 1. (a) Scanning electron micrograph and (b) transition electron micrograph of sample synthesized from polyvinyl alcohol and SEM photograph of sample synthesized from (c) poly vinyl pyrrolidone and (d) polyethylene glycol.

Table 1. Effect of UV-absorber on silica nanosphere formation

Sl. no.	Molar ratio of 2,2',4,4'-tetrahydroxy benzophenone	Particle size	Particle shape	Yield (%)
1.	0 (PVA)	500 μm–3 μm	Spherical	88
2.	0.2 (PVA)	3 μm	Leaves + spherical	65
3.	5 (PVA)	2–10 μm	Spherical	44
4.	10 (PVA)	2 μm	Dry leaves	58
5.	15 (PVA)	100–500 nm	Flag	63
6.	PVP	200 nm × 5–10 μm	Dry leaves	45
7.	PEG	200 nm × 5–10 μm	Fibers	64

A mechanism of silica hollow microsphere formation shows that poly vinyl pyrrolidone was aggregated together. Methyl trimethoxy silane (MTS) was formed as a layer over PVP. Tetraethyl orthosilicate was hydrolyzed in presence of ammonia and deposited over MTS. The final sphere was calcined at 550 °C to remove the organics.

Conclusions :

Silica hollow microsphere is synthesized from a poly-

mer, polyvinylalcohol. The particle sizes are ranging from 300 nm to 5 μm. Addition of UV-absorber and other polymers such as polyvinyl pyrrolidone and polyethylene glycol change the morphology into fibers. The synthesized material was characterized by scanning electron microscopy and transmission electron microscopy. Yields are in parabolic behavior with increasing the amount of UV-absorber.

Experimental

6 ml of tetraethyl orthosilicate (98%, Aldrich, USA) was mixed with 3.48 ml of methyl trimethoxy silane (98%, Aldrich, USA). 1.50 ml of distilled water was mixed with the above solution. The mixture was stirred for 5 min. 1.98 ml of aqueous ammonia (18–30%, Aldrich, USA) was mixed with 70 ml of distilled water and emulsified for another 10 min. The above silica solution was mixed with ammonia solution and homogenized at 1000 rpm for another 10 min. 0.836 g of polyvinyl alcohol was mixed with the above mixture and stirred for another 2 h. The final residue was centrifuged to separate and dried at 60 °C. The yield was 88% and subjected to physicochemical characterization. Similar experiments were conducted using polyethylene glycol (Mn 10,000, Aldrich, USA) and poly vinyl pyrrolidone (Mn 55,000, Aldrich, USA).

The particle size and shape were analyzed by a Topcon, SM-300 scanning electron microscope. The copper disc pasted with carbon tape and the sample was dispersed over the tape. The disc was coated with gold in ionization chamber. Transmission electron microscopic (TEM) studies were performed on a JEOL JSM-2000 EX electron microscope operated at 200 kV. The TEM sample was prepared by dipping a Cu grid coated with carbon films in sample suspension with water as solvent (solution was sonicated for 20 min).

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Note

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